
COGNITIVE DISTORTIONS AND PATHOLOGICAL GAMBLING AMONG BET PLAYERS IN MAKURDI METROPOLIS: MEDIATING ROLE OF FRUSTRATION

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Abstract

This study investigated cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players of Makurdi metropolis; the mediating role of frustration. The study adopted cross-sectional survey design using three hundred and eighty-four (384) bet players in Makurdi metropolis. They comprised of 331 (86.2%) males and 53 (13.8%) females. Their ages ranged from 24-55 years with a mean age of 39.159 years (SD=10.905). Multi-stage sampling was used to draw the participants. The Self-Debasing Cognitive Distortion Scale, Frustration Scale and the Pathological Gambling Diagnostic Form were used for data collection. Simple linear regression, Multiple linear regression, Process Mediation Analysis and Standard Multiple Regression Analysis were used to test hypotheses. The result indicated that there was a significant positive influence of cognitive distortion on pathological gambling among bet players. The result also indicated that there was a significant influence of frustration on pathological gambling among bet player. In terms of the dimensions, the result indicated that emotional intolerance, entitlement, discomfort, and achievement made significant positive contributions to pathological gambling among bet players. The result also indicated that frustration significantly mediated the influence of cognitive distortions on pathological gambling among bet players. Lastly, there was a significant joint influence of cognitive distortions and frustration on pathological gambling among bet players. It was concluded that frustration is a significant mediator between cognitive distortion and pathological gambling. It was recommended that clinical psychologists should collaborate with betting firms to create online notifications on all betting platforms such that bet players will be warned on the common predispositions and symptoms of cognitive distortion, such that they could

know their risk of becoming pathological gamblers if they are already experiencing distorted thought patterns.

Key Words: Cognitive Distortions, Frustration, Pathological Gambling, Bet Players

Background to the Study

Pathological gambling has become one of the most addictive yet under-intervened disorder among youths today. The disorder starts with typical gambling behaviour using tickets and tokens and proceeds to the stage of wagering money and valuables on an outcome that could occur by chance. Generally, gambling provides social and economic dividends and the increasing access to gambling platforms has increased the society's awareness of gambling opportunities (Dickerson et al., 2023; Monaghan & Derevensky, 2018) especially in Nigeria. In this form, gambling is considered social and financially fulfilling. However, gambling can become pathological when it deviates from the expected norm and becomes addictive to the individual. Pathological gambling is a common clinical problem in our contemporary society. This phenomenon has witnessed unprecedented rise in the past few years (Dickerson et al., 2023). In recent times, the culture of gambling has become legal and extensively supported. This is very common in many parts of Sub-Saharan Africa including Nigeria.

Nigeria has seen an unparallel surge in the number and sophistication of gambling activities taking place on a daily basis. The scope of the gambling investigation has expanded to include online lotteries, promotions, pool betting, sports betting, and casino slots. Nigeria leads the African continent in the number of Internet gamblers (Daniel et al., 2023). The gambling sector has been widely accepted across the country. The internet penetration is now estimated at 42% of the Nigerian population. That arises from different levels of economic, cultural, and technological factors influencing the region (Aguocha & George, 2021). Over 75% of Lagos residents aged 18–40 years participate in sports betting or online casino games regularly, particularly favoring football betting. Approximately 65% of adults in Abuja engage in some form of gambling. The betting industry in Abuja has gained significant development with increased internet access. Studies have shown that 60% of bettors in Ibadan focus on both local leagues and international tournaments (Adegbemi et al., 2023).

In Benue State, the issue of gambling has been heightened by the upsurge in unemployment, underemployment, availability of internet access via smartphones and economic hardship. In addition, the introduction of online lottery, sport betting, casino slots and diverse virtual games has changed the level of involvement considerably. Although some may intend to gamble at a safe level, they often lose control and fall victim of becoming addicted to gambling (Dickerson et al., 2023). Several studies have reported that involvement in pathological gambling may be a springboard for increase in criminal and delinquent behaviours (Oyebisiet al., 2022). Other studies have reported more severe negative consequences resulting from gambling. For instance, Tade (2024) reported that many gamblers commit suicide after losing their high stakes while some ruin their marriages and important social capital to gambling. Also, innumerable proportion of gamblers develop compulsive gambling problems which may manifest in both psychiatric (such as anxiety, depression, and sleep deprivation) as well as long-term physical conditions e.g. cardiovascular disease, peptic ulcer disease, and hypertension (Langa, 2020).

Ironically, in spite of these negative consequences, many residents of Makurdimetropolis still engage in one form of gambling or the other. Statistics have shown that in Makurdi, 38.6% of gamblers are driven by poverty and hardship, 21.9% by the motive to jack pot, 24.5% by leisure of the game, 11.9% by the habit to play modern gambling, while only 3.1% did not know why they play modern gambling (Aver & Aver, 2024).

Consequently, many factors have been implicated in the prediction of pathological gambling. Some of these factors are cognitive distortion and frustration. Cognitive distortion is one factor that is linked to gambling behaviour. Cognitive distortions are erroneous beliefs or fallacies, involved in the development and maintenance of problem gambling (Ladouceur, 2024). Broadly, these cognitive distortions are a set of false or exaggerated underlying beliefs that influence the automatic thoughts and behaviours a gambler experiences or displays during gambling. These beliefs are thought to arise from the gambler's misperception of randomness, prompting the individual to believe he or she can exert control over and correctly predict the outcome of a chance-oriented game. Motivated by the opportunity for monetary gain, the gambler's cognitive distortions prompt strategizing around the development of his or her gambling-related skill in an attempt to increase the likelihood of winning (Breen et al., 2021). Gambling-related cognitive distortions have been consistently found to be related to gambling problems. Previous literature has found a positive relationship between gambling-related cognitive distortions and problem gambling severity, where those with a greater severity of gambling problems endorse significantly more cognitive distortions compared to those with less severe gambling problems (Cunningham et al., 2024). For example, disordered gamblers and problem gamblers endorse considerably more cognitive distortions compared to both non-problem and social gamblers (Myrseth et al., 2020; Joukhador et al., 2024), even after controlling for genetic and environmental factors (Xian et al., 2019).

Recent studies have revealed a link between irrationality and increasing the size of bets (Delfabbro & Winefield, 2020). This link between irrationality and increasing the size of bets has been observed among pathological gamblers (Rickwood et al., 2020). The concept of control is an important element in cognitive distortions. For this reason, illusion of control is the most widely studied cognitive distortion in the literature (Lambos & Delfabbro, 2017). Gamblers, and especially pathological gamblers are particularly prone to perceiving illusory patterns (Gaissmaier et al., 2016). These cognitive illusions and distortions vary with culture. From the above studies, less can be understood of the cultural variations in cognitive distortions among gamblers in Benue State. More so, cognitive distortion likely predicts only a small percentage of the variance in pathological gambling. This indicates that there could be other factors that contribute to the development of pathological gambling among bet players.

Frustration is another likely determinant of pathological gambling. Frustration occurs when there exists a thwarting of goal-oriented behaviour. This often affects the emotions and consequent behaviours of the frustrated individual (Vastenkiste & Ryan, 2023). The experience of brief and intense emotions is an integral component of people's everyday life. Emotions influence how we make decisions and navigate our worlds, via bodily changes that prompt us to action. Frustration is a key negative emotion that has roots in disappointment, and it can be expressed in form of irritable distress in response to a limitation, exclusion, and/or failure (a state of dissatisfied insecurity). Frustration elicits negative affect, indicating that interests and interactions must be adjusted. It also initiates emotional tension or "arousal" to instigate defensive or aggressive behavioural responses, such as striving to reduce or eliminate the blocking agent or circumstances (Berkowitz, 2019).

Frustration is experienced when people encounter unresolved problems, such as contextual or psychological barriers or obstructions, which must be removed to fulfil personal goals, desires, drives, or needs. Technically, frustration is elicited when a goal-pursuit is not fulfilled at the expected time (Berkowitz, 2019). The most reliable trigger of frustration is an externally attributed omission of a rewarding event or item, and especially a perceived obstruction by an intentional antagonistic act (Jeronimus et al., 2015). The intensity of frustration is a function of the reward value of the frustrated goal (reward proximity and motivation), the degree of interference (partial/total), the number of interferences per unit time, and one's self-regulation abilities (Berkowitz, 2019). These features and risk factors for frustration are related to the antecedents of gambling behaviour. It is likely that people who feel frustrated in the search for viable sources of funds may resort to chance opportunities such as betting.

People with frustrated needs are likely to have higher chances of engaging in gambling behaviour. However, there is no explanation of the respective roles of the dimensions of frustration (emotional intolerance, entitlement, discomfort and achievement) on gambling behaviour. More so, the study could not explore frustration as a determinant of pathological gambling among bet players in Benue State. Other researchers have also associated frustration with problematic gambling (Mills et al., 2021; Vuorinen et al., 2022), but it is still unclear how frustration affects gambling behavior. It is feasible that frustration works in conjunction with certain gambling motives and accelerates the development of pathological gambling. Thus, thwarted intrinsic needs may drive toward more extrinsic rewards and motivate pathological gambling as a means of compensation.

Having established from previous studies (Lambos & Delfabbro, 2017; Berkowitz, 2019) that individuals high on cognitive distortions and frustration have an inclination to gamble than the general population, there is need to also understand if frustration can serve as a mediator between these variables. More so, it is likely that bet players who have distorted thought patterns will be more likely to gamble their resources to get more, if they have been frustrated at one or more points. It is uncommon for people to have distorted cognitive but resist the urge of gambling despite the need. However, when predisposed by frustration, the chances become very high that gambling will be resorted to as a fast medium to satisfy their needs. However, these claims and insinuations are yet to be established among bet players in Benue State. Therefore, this study investigated the mediating role of frustration between cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Cognitive Distortion and Pathological Gambling

In a quest to unveil the influence of cognitive distortions on pathological gambling, Ndukaihe et al. (2023) explored parental monitoring and age as pathways to understanding association between cognitive distortions and gambling problems among adolescents drawn from betting centers in Abakaliki, South-east Nigeria (N=237, Mean Age=17.03 years, SD=4.01). Data were obtained from the youths by means of the Inability to stop gambling scale, the Parental Monitoring Scale, and the South Oaks Gambling Screen-Revised for Adolescents. Moderated-mediation analysis results showed that age was positively associated with problem gambling and mediated the association between inability to stop gambling and gambling problems and this mediation was further moderated by parental monitoring. Specifically, the inability to stop gambling was linked to higher gambling problems through age for youths with low parental monitoring but not for those with high parental monitoring. They suggested that problem gambling prevention and intervention programs should target youths with low parental monitoring. This study has the strength of using high order analysis to unveil the mediators of the cognitive distortion and

gambling relationship, but the study failed to reveal the actual relationship between cognitive distortion and pathological gambling. This limitation is covered in the present study.

Phua et al. (2022) compared the cognitions of sports bettors and non-sports gamblers. A total of 713 participants were recruited of which 80 were sports bettors, 270 were non-sports gamblers, and 363 were non-gamblers. Cognitive distortions were measured using the Gamblers Belief's Questionnaire, which comprises two factors: Luck/Perseverance, and Illusion of Control. The results of a between-groups MANOVA showed that sports bettors recorded higher scores for Luck/Perseverance than non-gamblers and non-sports gamblers. Sports gamblers also recorded higher Illusion of Control scores than both non-gamblers and non-sports gamblers. Problem gambling was measured using the South Oaks Gambling Screen. One-way analysis of variance between the three groups showed sports bettors scores were higher than those of non-sports gamblers, and non-gamblers. These findings suggested that gamblers should not be treated as a homogenous group, and that greater attention should be placed on sports bettors in prevention and treatment efforts. The reviewed study has the unique difference of using different scales to measure cognitive distortions and gambling, from the ones to be used in the present study. Also, it used MANOVA for analysis while the present study used regression analysis.

Nigro et al. (2022) investigated the interplay between cognitive distortions related to gambling, temporal perspective, and chasing behaviour in a sample of habitual gamblers. Two hundred and fifty-five adults took part in the study. The participants completed the South Oaks Gambling Screen (SOGS), the Gambling Related Cognitions Scale (GRCS), the 14-item Consideration of Future Consequences scale (CFC-14), and performed a computerized task assessing chasing behaviour. Participants were randomly assigned to three experimental conditions (Control, Loss, and Win). Hierarchical logistic regression analysis showed that the decision to chase depended on scores on the CFC-14 Immediate scale and the GRCS dimensions Gambling Expectancies and Interpretative Bias. Hierarchical linear regression analysis indicated that, chasing frequency was affected by loss condition, distortions related to gambling expectancies and predictive control, as well as by myopia for the future. Interestingly, the results of path analysis clearly indicated that some cognitions related to gambling predict chasing frequency not only directly, but also indirectly via shortened time horizon. Notably, gambling severity did not predict either the decision to chase, or the chasing persistence. These findings provided further evidence that non-chasers and chasers seem to belong to two quite distinct subtypes of gamblers. They suggested that such a difference could be useful for targeting more effective intervention strategies in gambling disorder treatment. However, the reviewed study was not conducted using a sample of gamblers in Makurdi metropolis. Thus, the external validity of the study is largely limited.

Frustration and Gambling Behaviour

Hagfors et al. (2023) analyzed the links between gambling motives and problem gambling using a longitudinal study design. The moderating effect of the frustration of basic psychological needs was also assessed. The study sample with 1,022 participants (48.43% female, Mage=49.50 years) was surveyed at three timepoints (T1–T3) in 6-month intervals. The Problem Gambling Severity Index (PGSI) was used to measure problem gambling and need frustration was assessed with the Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale (BPNSFS). The data were analyzed using a multilevel mixed-effects regression model where PGSI was the outcome variable. Gambling motives and need frustration were the predictors while psychological distress (measured with the 5-Item Mental Health Inventory, MHI-5), offshore/onshore online gambling, and socio-demographic factors were used as control variables. All the motives predicted problem gambling

individually over time. In contrast, motives to escape, to win money, and to compete along with need frustration predicted problem gambling over time in the full model. In addition, money motive and need frustration had an interaction effect so that higher need frustration combined with money motive predicted more severe gambling problems. The results of the study provided a valuable longitudinal perspective on gambling motives, frustration of basic psychological needs, and gambling problems which can be used to develop and improve treatment efforts and programs of problem gambling. This study suffers the criticism that it adopted a longitudinal design as opposed to the cross-sectional design used in the present study.

Vuorinen et al. (2022) analyzed how need satisfaction and frustration relate to the severity of gambling and gaming problems. A survey study with 18–75-year-old Finnish participants (N=1530; 50.33% male) was conducted in April 2021. Basic psychological needs were measured with the Basic Psychological Need Satisfaction and Frustration Scale, mental health issues with the five-item Mental Health Inventory, gambling problems with the Problem Gambling Severity Index, and gaming problems with the Internet Gaming Disorder Test. Zero-inflated negative binomial analyses were conducted to examine how satisfaction and frustration of basic psychological needs, together with mental health issues, are associated with gaming and gambling problems. Mental health issues were associated with gambling and gaming problems, but this association became nonsignificant when basic psychological needs were added to the model. However, better mental health still was associated with the absence of gaming problems. While need satisfaction had no association with the absence of gaming or gambling problems, need frustration was associated with increases in the severity of both gaming and gambling problems. They concluded that frustration of basic psychological needs for autonomy, relatedness, and competence is associated with both gambling and gaming problems and should be considered when developing treatment and support for those who experience such problems. This study failed to cover local populations in Makurdi metropolis, it was limited to Finnish gamblers.

Livazovic and Bojic (2019) examined the roles of sociodemographic traits, family quality and risk behaviour in adolescent problem gambling, with focus on the psychological, social and financial consequences from the socioecological model approach such as frustration. This model emphasized the most important risk-protective factors in the development and maintenance of problem gambling on an individual level, a relationship level, as well as a community and societal level. The research was done using the Canadian Adolescent Gambling Inventory with a sample of 366 participants, 239 females (65.3%) using descriptive statistics and t-test, ANOVA, correlation and hierarchical regression analysis. Males reported significantly higher gambling consequences on all scales and significantly more risk behaviour. Age was significant for psychological consequences, problem gambling and risk behaviour with older participants scoring higher. Students with lower school success reported significantly higher psychological consequences of gambling, higher risk behaviour activity and lower family life satisfaction. The psychological, financial and social consequences were positively correlated with problem gambling. Age, gender, school success and the father's education level were significant predictors of problem gambling, with older male adolescents who struggle academically and have lower educated fathers being at greater risk. Results indicated an important relation between adolescent gambling behaviour and very serious psychological, social and financial consequences such as frustration. Also, that there was a constellation of risk factors that likely place certain individuals at high risk for problem gambling. Despite the salience of the reviewed study, it was carried out outside the scope of Makurdi metropolis.

Frustration Mediating between Cognitive Distortions and Pathological Gambling

Cunningham et al. (2024) explored the relationship between problem gambling severity and cognitive distortions about gambling with regards to frustration tendencies. A representative sample of problem gamblers (n=5,766) was asked about cognitive distortions related to gambling. A positive association between gambling severity and cognitive distortions emerged, even when the variables associated with participants' demographic characteristics were accounted for. The study demonstrated that the relationship between problem gambling severity and cognitive distortions does exist in the general population of problem gamblers and was increased when gamblers experience frustration in their pursued goals. This finding emphasized the key role that cognitive distortions may play in the development and maintenance of pathological gambling for frustrated gamblers. However, the study was not carried out in Makurdi metropolis.

Maclaren et al. (2024) investigated if gambling motives and cognitive distortions mediate the effects of personality on problem gambling in electronic gambling machine players. A community sample of 273 people who play Electronic Gambling Machines frequently was collected from Brandon, Manitoba, Canada. Participants completed standard measures of problem gambling (Problem Gambling Severity Index), gambling motives (Gambling Motives Questionnaire), cognitive distortions (Informational Biases Scale), and personality (NEO PI-R). Regression of problem gambling severity scores onto cognitive distortions, 4 gambling motives, and 4 personality traits found significant direct effects of cognitive distortion, coping and financial motives, and low positive emotions facet of extraversion. Mediation analyses found that cognitive distortion mediated indirect effects of high scores on withdrawal-related facets of neuroticism, and the coping motive mediated effects of low scores on industriousness-related facets of conscientiousness. They concluded broad personality dispositions known to elevate risk of problem gambling may have their effects through mechanisms of escapist motivation for gambling and distorted beliefs about gambling. This Canadian study rather used cognitive distortion as a mediator as opposed to the use of frustration as is done in the present study.

Cognitive Distortions, Frustration and Pathological Gambling

Bankole et al. (2019) assessed personality characteristics and financial strain as a determinants of gambling behaviour among youth in Nigeria. Three instruments were used in the study which include Gambling behaviour scale used in measuring prevalence and pattern of gambling behaviour, Big five personality scale used in assessing personality domain of an individual and the financial strain scale used in measuring the rate of financial strain experienced by people. Three hundred and twenty participants (320) were used in this study but two hundred and ninety-seven participants (297) responses were retrieved for analysis. Hypotheses were tested using regression analysis and independent t-test and the result were discussed according to literatures. It was concluded from the study, that personality characteristics and financial strain predicts gambling behaviour and also there exists sex differences in gambling behaviour. As a result of this, it was however recommended that youths are to be trained on how to improve their behavioural attitudes and should be well guided so as to avoid gambling because it has serious effects on their psychological health and overall well-being. This indigenous study measured cognitive distortion and frustration indirectly via personality and financial constraints; a major limitation covered in the present study.

Oyeleke et al. (2017) investigated the influence of personality traits and cognitive distortions on pathological gambling among lottery gamblers in Ibadan, Nigeria. The research was

conducted on a group of 469 (383 males; 86 females) gamblers in Ibadan using three psychometric scales: Gambler's Belief Questionnaire (GBQ), Big Five Personality Scale; Cognitive Distortions Scale. Results revealed that cognitive distortions had significant influence on pathological gambling. Neuroticism, education, and age all independently predicted pathological gambling while occupation and educational qualification jointly predicted pathological gambling. Cognitive distortions, neuroticism, education and age were important determinants of pathological gambling. They recommended that gamblers require a comprehensive, cognitive restructuring to desensitize them from pathological gambling. Also, that in future, extended interdisciplinary research should be carried out on psychological profiling among pathological gamblers to optimize comprehensive personality assessment.

Research Hypotheses

The researcher postulated the following hypotheses which were tested in the study:

- i. Cognitive distortions will significantly influence pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.
- ii. Frustration will significantly influence pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.
- iii. Frustration will significantly mediate between cognitive distortion and pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.
- iv. Cognitive distortions and frustration will jointly influence pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Design

This study employed the use of Cross-sectional Survey design to investigate the cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players of Makurdi metropolis; the mediating role of frustration. A cross-sectional survey collects data to make inferences about a population of interest (universe) at one point in time. It has been described as snapshots of the populations about which they gather data (Lavrakas, 2018). The design has a great advantage because it can be implemented with a relatively fewer resources and it is recommended for the purpose of large samples approaches (Shindi, 2017). In this study, the independent variable was cognitive distortion, the mediating variable was frustration while the dependent variable was pathological gambling.

Population

Currently the population of bet players in Makurdi metropolis is not certain. This could be due to the fluctuating figures of people who initiate betting or stop betting on daily basis. Moreover, there is no specific record or registry for recording bet players in Benue state.

3.3.1 Sample Size Determination

The sample size for this study was determined using the sampling formula for unknown populations developed by Cochran (2007):

$n = z^2 pq / e^2$, where

n = the sample size

z = the 95% level of confidence corresponding to a z value of 1.96

p=the estimated proportion of the population (0.5)

q=the inverse of p i.e. 1-p

e=the tolerated margin of error (.05 or 5%)

Therefore, the formula is applied as follows:

$$n = \frac{z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

$$n = \frac{(1.96)^2 0.5(0.5)}{(.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.84 \times 0.25}{0.0025}$$

$$n = \frac{0.96}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 384$$

Therefore, the sample for the study was 384 pathological gamblers.

Sampling Technique

For the purpose of this study, the Multistage sampling technique was used. This technique was used because sampling was carried out in stages. At the first stage, the geographical locations in Makurdi metropolis where gambling is predominant were purposefully sampled. At the second stage, the gamblers were accidentally sampled at their respective points of betting in gambling shops. Lastly, only those who met the criteria for pathological gambling were considered for the study.

Participants

The participants for this study were three hundred and eighty-four (384) bet players in Makurdi metropolis. They comprised of 331 (86.2%) males and 53 (13.8%) were females. Their ages ranged from 24-55 year with a mean age of 39.159 years (SD=10.905). In terms of their religion, 220 (57.3%) were Christians, 73 (19%) were Muslim while 91 (23.7%) were practicing traditional religion. As for their ethnic groups, 200 (52.1%) were Tiv, 107 (27.9%) were Idoma while 77 (20%) were from other ethnic groups. As for their marital statuses, 117 (30.5%) were single, 103 (26.8%) were married, 80 (20.8%) were divorced while 84 (21.9%) were widowed. As for the duration of gambling, 77 (20.1%) gambled for less than a year, 154 (40.1%) gambled for 1-10 years while 153 (39.8%) gambled for over 10 years. As for their gambling frequency, 151 (39.3%) gambled daily, 179 (46.6%) gambled weekly while 54 (14.1%) gambled monthly.

Instruments

- i. The demographic variables assessed in the study include; sex, age, religion, ethnic group, marital status and duration of gambling.
- ii. Cognitive Distortion was measured using the Self-Debasing Cognitive Distortion Scale developed by Ara (2016). The scale was developed to measure the various forms of

automatic/negative distorted thoughts/cognitions among adults. The uni-dimensional 16-item scale is measured on a 5-point Likert Format of 0 (never) to 4 (most often). The scale is scored such that the scores of each individual on each item is summed up. The highest score on the scale is 64 and the lowest score can be 0. High scores indicate high cognitive distortions while low scores indicate low cognitive distortions. None of the items on the scale are reverse-scored. The author reported an alpha coefficient of .73. The present study reported an alpha coefficient of .86. Face and content validities were established by three lecturers in the department of Psychology who have vast knowledge of psychometrics. Sample of items include; “If something goes wrong, I think it is my fault”, “I think nothing will ever work out for me”.

- iii. Frustration was measured using the Frustration Scale developed by Harrington (2005). The scale measures people’s disposition to thwarted goals in their daily lives. The scale consists of 32 items and is rated on a five-point Likert scale of 1 (Strongly Disagree) to 5 (Strongly Agree). The dimensions of the scale are; Emotional intolerance (8 items), Entitlement (8 items), Discomfort (8 items) and Achievement (8 items). The total score on the scale is obtained by summing the scores of each individual on all the items on the scale. High scores indicate high levels of frustration and low scores indicate low levels of frustration. The author obtained a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of .94 for the full scale, .88 for Discomfort intolerance, .85 for Entitlement, .87 for Emotional intolerance, and .84 for the Achievement subscale. The present study obtained an overall coefficient of .72 while the subscales had .84, .74, .73 and .76 for Emotional intolerance, Entitlement, Discomfort intolerance, and Achievement. Face and content validities were established by three lecturers in the department of Psychology who have vast knowledge of psychometrics. Sample of items include; “I can’t bear been taken for granted”, “I can’t bear feeling like am losing my mind”.
- iv. Pathological Gambling was measured using an extract of the DSM-V Pathological Gambling Diagnostic Form drawn by Ademola (2016). The 9-item pathological gambling diagnostic form is scored with 0 (No) and 1 (Yes). According to the Diagnostic Manual scaling, the score of 4 or more indicates the presence of “pathological gambling” while scores less than 3 indicate “no disorder”. Hence the total score of each respondent is calculated and scaled as: 0–3 (No Pathological Gambling) and 4–9 (Pathological Gambling). Thus, high scores indicate high gambling behaviour and vice versa. The author obtained a Cronbach’s alpha of .73 while the present study obtained .87. Face and content validities were established by three lecturers in the department of Psychology who have vast knowledge of psychometrics. Sample of items include; “Have you become restless or irritable when trying to cut down or stop gambling?”, “Have you lied to your family or others to hide the extent of your gambling?”

Pilot Study

The instruments used in this study were pilot tested using 74 residents of Mkar, Gboko-South and Yandev in Gboko Local Government Area. The results revealed that their ages ranged from 20-48 years with the mean age of 31.31 years (SD=4.98). As for their sex, 64 (86.5%) were male while 10 (13.5%) were female residents. Considering their religion, 70 (94.6%) were Christians while 4 (5.4%) were Muslims. In terms of their ethnic groups, 49 (66.2%) were Tiv, 13 (17.6%) were Idoma while the remaining 12 (16.2%) were from other ethnic groups. As for their marital status, 44 (59.5%) were single, 20 (27%) were married, 7 (9.5%) were divorced while 3

(4%) were widowed. Lastly, as for their duration of gambling, 27 (36.5%) gambled below 1 year, 34 (45.9%) gambled between 1-10 years, while the remaining 13 (17.5%) gambled above 10 years.

The result showed that the Self-Debasing Cognitive Distortion Scale yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .84. Furthermore, the item total correlations for each of the items in the scale were above the set norm of .30, with item 11 having the highest value of .97 and item 14 with the lowest value of .36. This implies that the instrument is fit for use in the main study.

The result also showed that the Frustration Scale yielded a Cronbach's alpha coefficient of .81 for the overall scale while emotional intolerance, entitlement, discomfort and achievement had .79, .71, .81 and .77. Furthermore, the item total correlations for each of the items in the scale were above the set norm of .30, with item 9 having the highest value of .90 and item 3 with the lowest value of .32. This also implies that the instrument is fit for use in the main study.

Lastly, the result revealed that the Pathological Gambling Diagnostic Form yielded an alpha coefficient of .78. Furthermore, the item total correlation for each of the items in the scale was above the set norm of .30 (Cristobal et al., 2007), with item 5 having the highest value of .89 and item 1 with the lowest value of .42. This implies that the instrument is fit for use in the main study.

Procedure

This study was carried out in Makurdi metropolis. Specifically, the researcher visited betshops at Northbank, Wadata, Modern Market, Wurukum, Highlevel, Gyado Villa and International Market. A letter of introduction was obtained from the Head of Psychology Department. The letter was used to seek and obtain the consent of the targeted bet players before been exposed to the questionnaire. The researcher prepared a total of 500 copies of the questionnaire for administration which were in excess of the estimated sample. This was done to enable the researcher obtain a reasonable sample (384) that will likely meet the criteria for pathological gambling. The researcher trained 4 research assistants (postgraduate students) who assisted by visiting bet shops in Makurdi metropolis where bet players come on daily basis to gamble. During the administration process, the respondents were informed that their responses would be used only for research purpose. After the administration of the 500 copies of the questionnaire, the 384 filled copies that were scored and found to meet the criteria for pathological gambling were considered for statistical analysis while those who do not meet the criteria were discarded.

Data Analysis

For the purpose of data analysis, the researcher used both descriptive and inferential statistics. In this study, the descriptive statistics such as mean, standard deviation, frequencies and simple percentages were used to describe the respondents. Simple linear regression was used to test hypotheses one, Multiple linear regression was used for hypothesis two, hypothesis three was tested using Process Mediation Analysis while hypothesis four was tested using Standard Multiple Regression Analysis.

Results

Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses postulated in this study were tested using Simple linear regression, Multiple linear regression, Hayes Process Macro and Standard Multiple Regression. The results are presented in the following tables:

Table 1: Summary of Simple Linear Regression showing the influence of cognitive distortions on pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Variables	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	sig.
Constant	.479	.229	113.690	1,382		32.519	.000
Cognitive Distortions					.479	10.663	.000

The result presented in table 1 indicated that there was a significant positive influence of cognitive distortion on pathological gambling among bet players [$R^2=.229$, $F(1,382)=113.690$, $p<.001$]. The result further indicated that cognitive distortions explained 22.9% of the variation in pathological gambling. This means that bet players who have cognitive distortions will be more likely to engage in pathological gambling behaviour. Thus, hypothesis one was supported.

Table 2: Summary of Multiple Linear Regression showing the influence of frustration on pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Variables	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.598	.358	19935.400	4,379	.000		
Emotional Intolerance					.368	11.861	.000
Entitlement				.456	14.114	.000	
Discomfort				.407	11.396	.000	
Achievement				.434	12.792	.000	

The result presented in table 2 indicated that there was a significant influence of frustration on pathological gambling among bet player [$R^2=.358$, $F(4,379)=19935.400$, $p<.001$]. The result further indicated that frustration explained 35.8% of the variation in pathological gambling. In terms of the dimensions, the result indicated that emotional intolerance ($\beta=.368$, $t=11.861$, $p<.001$), entitlement ($\beta=.456$, $t=14.114$, $p<.001$), discomfort ($\beta=.407$, $t=11.396$, $p<.001$), and achievement ($\beta=.434$, $t=12.792$, $p<.001$) made significant positive contributions to pathological gambling among bet players. Thus, hypothesis two was also supported.

Table 3: Summary of Hayes Process Macro showing the mediating role of frustration between cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Variables	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	sig.	LLCI	ULCI
Constant	.561	.315	87.422	2,381		16.216	.000		
Cognitive Distortions					.268	11.690	.000	-.3134	-.2232
Frustration					.124	6.882	.000	.0883	.1589
Int_1(X*M)					.018	.017	.000	-.0133	-.0561

The result displayed in table 3 shows that frustration significantly mediated the influence of cognitive distortions on pathological gambling among bet players [$R^2=.315$, $F(2,381)=87.422$, $Int_1(X*M)$ ($\beta=.018$, $t=.017$, $p<.001$)]. The result indicated that both cognitive distortions ($\beta=.268$, $t=11.690$, $p<.001$) and frustration ($\beta=.124$, $t=6.882$, $p<.001$) are significant predictors of pathological gambling. Thus, hypothesis three was also supported.

Table 4: Summary of Standard Multiple Regression showing the joint influence of cognitive distortions and frustration on pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Variables	R	R ²	F	df	β	t	Sig.
Constant	.561	.315	87.422	2,381		16.216	.000
Cognitive Distortion					.497	11.690	.000
Frustration					.292	6.882	.000

The result presented in table 4 indicated that there was a significant joint influence of cognitive distortions and frustration on pathological gambling among bet players [$R^2=.315$, $F(2,381)=87.422$, $p<.001$]. The result further indicated that both cognitive distortions and frustration jointly explained 31.5% of the variation in pathological gambling. This implies that gambling to a pathological level is a composite function of numerous factors. Thus, hypothesis four was supported.

Discussion

Hypothesis one was tested to find out if cognitive distortions will significantly influence pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis. Findings indicated that cognitive distortions significantly influenced pathological gambling among bet players. Cognitive distortions entail thought patterns that are exaggerated and negatively biased, causing people to perceive reality inaccurately. They can lead to negative feelings and behaviors, such as anxiety, depression, and low self-esteem. In relation to gambling, bet players who have distorted thoughts are likely to engage in irrational wagering of funds. Therefore, it is not uncommon for cognitive distortions to induce pathological gambling behaviour among bet players. This implies that people who already have distorted thoughts will be high targets for pathological gambling. This finding thus agrees with Ndukaihe et al. (2023) who found an association between inability to stop gambling and gambling problems. Similarly, Phua et al. (2022) showed that sports bettors recorded higher scores for luck/perseverance than non-gamblers and non-sports gamblers. Their findings also revealed that sports gamblers also recorded higher illusion of control scores than both non-gamblers and non-sports gamblers. Another related finding by Nigro et al. (2022) indicated that, chasing frequency was affected by distortions related to gambling expectancies and predictive control. In addition, some cognitions related to gambling predicted chasing frequency.

Hypothesis two was tested to find out if frustration will significantly influence pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis. Findings indicated that frustration significantly influenced pathological gambling among bet players. Frustration is a feeling that one's goals are thwarted by external obstacles or personal limitations. It is common place for frustrated individuals to be confused, have disorganized thoughts and engage in unwarranted behaviours such as pathological gambling. The finding implies that managing the frustration of potential gamblers will reduce their tendency to gamble pathologically, Thus, this finding tallies with Hagfors et al. (2023) who found that need frustration predicted problem gambling. Relatedly, Vuorinen et al. (2022) revealed that need frustration was associated with increases in the severity of both gaming and gambling problems. Earlier studies by Stremme et al. (2021) and Livazovic and Bojic (2019) indicated associations between gambling behaviour and frustration.

Hypothesis three was tested to find out if frustration will significantly mediate between cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis. Findings indicated that frustration significantly and fully mediated between cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players. This finding implies that clinical psychologists will need to monitor the frustration levels of gamblers, since it was found to expedite the influence of cognitive distortion on gambling behaviour. This finding agrees with Cunningham et al. (2024) who demonstrated that the relationship between problem gambling severity and cognitive distortions was increased when gamblers experience frustration in their pursued goals. Also, Maclaren et al. (2024) revealed that problem gambling severity was associated with cognitive distortions, and indirectly through frustrated motives.

Hypothesis four was tested to find out if cognitive distortions and frustration will jointly influence pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis. Findings indicated that cognitive distortions and frustration jointly influenced pathological gambling among bet players. The implication of this finding is that, irrational thoughts and frustrations will be flagged red by clinical psychologists as prime predispositions to gambling. This finding tallies with Bankole et al. (2019) who revealed that frustration and cognitive strain predicted gambling behaviour. Another study by Oyeleke et al. (2017) revealed that cognitive distortions and frustrated needs had significant joint influence on pathological gambling.

Conclusion

Based on the findings obtained from the present study, the following inferences were drawn:

- i. Cognitive distortions are significant antecedents of pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.
- ii. Frustration is a significant predictor of pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.
- iii. Frustration is a mediator between cognitive distortions and pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.
- iv. Cognitive distortions and frustration are significant joint predictors of pathological gambling among bet players in Makurdi metropolis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings obtained from this study, the researcher has made the following recommendations;

- i. Clinical psychologists should collaborate with betting firms to create online notifications on all betting platforms such that bet players will be warned on the common predispositions and symptoms of cognitive distortion, such that they could know their risk of becoming pathological gamblers if they are already experiencing distorted thought patterns.
- ii. In addition, since frustration and distorted thoughts are risk factors not just for pathological gambling but also for clinical depression, betting firms should employ the services of clinical psychologists who would provide psychological support to such bet players who have bet-related need for support.
- iii. Addiction professionals are encouraged by this study to include need frustration assessment in the process of managing clients who present for bet-related addiction services since frustration was noted in the present study to mediate cognitive distortions and pathological gambling.

Contributions to Knowledge

This study has identified novel and significant findings that are salient to the practice of clinical psychology:

- i. The study has validated the connection between cognitive factors and engagement in pathological gambling. This opposes the theories that sees gambling as been influenced solely by one's social environment, but it also supports theories that explain the development of pathological gambling from a personal/cognitive perspective especially the cognitive behavioral theory.
- ii. This study has also confirmed the presence of pathological gamblers in Makurdi metropolis. This finding is unique and distinguishes this study from related ones conducted in Makurdi. More so, as an indigenous study, it adds value to the few existing local studies conducted in Makurdi metropolis.

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